

1 **A study on cadmium immobilization by bacterial consortia: *Achromobacter insuavis* SL8 and *Enterobacter***
2 ***cancerogenus* SL12**

3 **1. Detailed methods of soil bacterial isolation and identification.**

4 Each soil sample (1 g) was suspended in 100mL of 0.85% saline solution (pH 7.2), shaken at 28°C and 150 rpm for 2 h to fully dissociate
5 bacteria from soil particles. The resulting suspension was serially diluted, and aliquots were spread on Luria-Bertani (LB) agar plates (10 g of
6 tryptone, 5 g of yeast extract, 10 g of NaCl, 20 g agar per liter, pH 7) supplemented with 0.1 mM Cd(II) (as CdCl₂), then incubated at 28°C for
7 one week to isolate single colonies. To assess bacterial Cd(II) resistance, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) assays were conducted on both
8 LB and minimal salts (MS) agar media (10 g of glucose, 2.8 g of Na₂HPO₄, 1 g of KH₂PO₄, 0.5 g of (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.1 g of MgCl₂·6H₂O, 0.05 g of
9 CaCl₂·4H₂O, 0.5 mg of EDTA-2Na, 0.01 mg of FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.01mg of ZnSO₄·7H₂O, 0.003 mg of MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.03 mg of H₃BO₃, 0.02 mg of
10 CoCl₂·6H₂O, 0.001mg of CuCl₂·2H₂O, 0.002 mg of NiCl₂·6H₂O, 0.003 mg of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 15 g agar per liter, pH 7.2) amended with varying
11 concentrations of CdCl₂.

12 For strain identification, the 16S rRNA gene sequences of purified isolates were amplified with universal primers 27F (5'-
13 AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'), followed by sequencing at Tsingke Company (Beijing,

14 China). The obtained sequences were aligned and compared using the BLAST program on GenBank (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BLAST>). A
 15 phylogenetic tree was constructed via the neighbor-joining method in MEGA 5.1 software, with branch stability assessed by bootstrap analysis
 16 based on 1,000 replications.

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18 **Table S1. Comparative analysis of differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) across four groups: SL8 with Cd (A), SL12 with Cd (B),**
 19 **coculture strains without Cd (C), and coculture strains with Cd (D), highlighting the most significantly enriched GO terms ($P < 0.05$).**

ID	Description	A_vs_D_ regulated	B_vs_D_ regulated	C_vs_D_ regulated	Function
A0A5Q2K0J4	Chorismate synthase	up	up	up	Amino acid transport and metabolism
A0A6J5AB12	HTH-type transcriptional regulator FarR	up	up	up	Transcription
A0A5Q2K0C4	Exopolyphosphatase	up	down	up	Nucleotide transport and metabolism; Signal transduction mechanisms; Inorganic ion transport and metabolism
A0A484YC41	Protein YgiW	up	down	up	Function unknown

A0A5Q2K6S5	Ohr family peroxiredoxin	up	down	up	Defense mechanisms
A0A5Q2KC77	3,4-dihydroxy-2-butanone 4-phosphate synthase	up	down	up	Coenzyme transport and metabolism
A0A5Q2K0U0	Ecotin	up	down	up	Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones
A0A484WT41	Hypoxanthine phosphoribosyl transferase	up	down	up	Nucleotide transport and metabolism
A0A6J4ZR00	Uncharacterized protein	down	up	up	Cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning
A0A6J5ARW2	Catalase	down	up	up	Inorganic ion transport and metabolism

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21 **Table S2. Comparative analysis of metabolite profiles across four groups: SL8 with Cd (A), SL12 with Cd (B), coculture strains without**
 22 **Cd (C), and coculture strains with Cd (D).**

Name	A_vs_D regulated	B_vs_D regulated	C_vs_D regulated	A_vs_D log ₂ FC	B_vs_D log ₂ FC	C_vs_D log ₂ FC
L-Dihydroanticapsin	up	up	up	0.32	0.58	1.11
N-Heptanoylhomoserinelactone	up	up	up	4.85	0.29	11.30
Geranylacetone	up	up	up	0.43	1.90	5.86

N6-Acetyl-L-lysine	up	up	up	0.74	2.10	2.28
16-hydroxyhexadecanoicacid	up	up	up	0.93	2.85	1.68
Methionyl-Valine	up	up	up	0.06	0.10	0.22
(-)-GlyceollinI	up	up	up	0.16	0.22	2.19
Alnustone	up	up	up	0.16	0.18	1.02
5'-[(3-aminopropyl) methylamino]-5'-deoxyadenosine	up	up	up	0.36	0.26	4.08
Valyl-Valine	up	up	up	0.53	4.59	3.45
Glutathionylaminopropylcadaverine	up	up	up	1.44	0.98	2.21
Minoxidil	up	up	up	0.14	0.10	0.17
2,5-Diamino-6-(5-phospho-D-ribosylamino) pyrimidin-4(3H)-one	up	up	up	0.60	0.93	2.05
3-Dimethylallyl-4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate	up	up	up	0.27	0.33	1.21
ValPro	up	up	up	0.13	0.14	0.45
Cinnzeylanol	up	up	up	0.10	0.11	0.44
Cytidine	up	up	up	0.52	0.15	0.93
octyl2-acetamido-2-deoxy-alpha-D-glucoopyranoside	up	up	up	0.40	0.93	2.46
butalbital	up	up	up	0.45	0.47	6.61
PE (17:1(9Z)/0:0)	up	up	up	0.83	1.94	1.31
3,5-tetradecadienoate	up	up	up	0.22	0.20	1.10
5-Hydroxymethylcytidine	up	up	up	0.17	0.39	1.33
Acetyl-DL-Valine	up	up	up	0.35	1.39	0.68
5-Methoxy-DL-tryptophan	up	up	up	0.28	0.17	0.20
L-Glutamine	up	up	up	0.18	0.21	2.48
IleGlySerPro	up	up	up	0.12	0.15	0.50
2-methyl-1,3-Cyclohexanedione	up	up	up	0.74	1.98	1.10
Dodecenoylcarnitine	up	up	up	0.89	0.83	3.17
(S)-N-Methylcoclaurine	up	up	up	0.18	0.10	2.16
Methohexital	up	up	up	0.20	0.14	1.13
PGF1 α Alcohol	up	up	up	1.41	0.97	1.92
Diphenhydramine	up	up	up	0.22	0.10	3.20
N1-Methyl-2-pyridone-5-carboxamide	up	up	up	1.05	0.28	1.39
Perillicacid	up	up	up	0.11	0.50	0.82
Phenanthrene-1,2-oxide	up	up	up	0.91	0.26	1.31
quinamideisopropylidene	up	up	up	0.22	0.20	1.78
7-Methylguanine	up	up	up	0.70	0.79	1.52

Uridinediphosphate-N-acetylgalactosamine	up	up	up	1.50	1.91	33.22
Methysergide	up	up	up	0.20	0.28	4.08
2-Dehydro-3-deoxy-D-arabino-heptonate7-phosphate	up	up	up	0.56	1.86	2.24
(4aR,10bS)-Normaritidine	down	up	up	-0.51	0.33	0.50
1,5-dideoxy-1,5-imino-D-galactitol	down	up	up	-0.27	0.56	0.19
Pyrrolidonecarboxylicacid	down	up	up	-0.39	1.99	2.02
Threoninyl-Lysine	down	up	up	-0.71	0.45	3.55
Caprylicacid	down	up	up	-0.78	3.51	1.85
LysLeu	down	up	up	-3.90	0.74	1.78
L-Lysine	down	up	up	-0.18	1.23	5.00
Isovalericacid	down	up	up	-0.42	1.01	1.56
2-ISOPRENYL-3-HYDROXY-5-METHYL-a-PYRONE	down	up	up	-0.33	0.50	0.83
Cortisone	down	up	up	-0.39	0.69	0.73
Isoleucyl-Alanine	down	up	up	-0.88	0.45	1.15
beta-Alanyl-L-arginine	down	up	up	-0.41	1.07	0.58
Asp-Phe	down	up	up	-2.48	0.30	1.40
Threoninyl-Tryptophan	down	up	up	-1.62	2.07	3.18
nicotinicacidD-ribonucleotide	down	up	up	-0.61	4.50	7.88
3alpha-Hydroxy-3,5-dihydromonacolinLacid	down	up	up	-0.10	0.42	0.99
2-Amino-2-methyl-1,3-propanediol	down	up	up	-0.25	0.66	0.32
2-amino-6-(hydroxymethyl)-7,8-dihydropteridin-4-ol	down	up	up	-0.10	0.45	0.93
Lobelanine	down	up	up	-0.40	0.38	0.31
Uridine	down	up	up	-1.02	0.31	1.27
3-(4'-Methylthio) butylmalicacid	down	up	up	-0.52	1.03	1.26
13(S)-HODE	down	up	up	-0.20	2.74	2.58
1-(Methylthio)-3-pentanone	down	up	up	-0.98	0.42	1.22
4-Aminobutanoate	down	up	up	-0.30	0.49	0.23
2,5-Diamino-6-(5'-phosphoribosylamino)-4-pyrimidineone	down	up	up	-0.29	9.50	31.01
Isoleucyl-Lysine	down	up	up	-3.00	0.50	0.92
5-Methoxyindoleacetate	down	up	up	-0.19	0.30	0.60
N6-Hydroxy-L-lysine	down	up	up	-0.27	0.57	1.18
2'-Deoxyuridine	down	up	up	-0.75	1.53	2.92
gamma-glutamyl-ethylamide	down	up	up	-0.33	0.50	0.39
PrecursorZ	down	up	up	-0.54	1.17	6.32

Lysyl-Proline	down	up	up	-1.06	1.43	2.78
Deoxyloganin	down	up	up	-0.08	0.29	2.28
DL-Leucine	down	up	up	-0.75	0.52	1.46
Guanine	down	up	up	-2.52	0.22	0.71
N.alpha.-Acetyl-L-lysine	down	up	up	-0.16	0.21	0.34
14-hydroxy-heneicosanoicacid	down	up	up	-0.96	6.60	1.14
Cyclooctatin	down	up	up	-0.63	1.03	0.90
Lys-Lys	down	up	up	-0.37	0.82	3.68
(E)-2-Tridecene-4,6,8-triyn-1-ol	down	up	up	-0.39	1.15	1.86
2-Methyl-1-Pyrroline	down	up	up	-0.20	0.52	1.06
ProstaglandinA2	down	up	up	-0.56	1.64	3.20
O-Desmethylnaproxen	down	up	up	-1.81	3.11	4.13
Pseudaminicacid	down	up	up	-0.52	1.01	1.46
4'-Oxolividamine	down	up	up	-1.20	1.13	2.39
Scopolamine	down	up	up	-0.38	1.48	2.11
L-Xylo-hexulonolactone	down	up	up	-1.09	1.06	2.87
O-beta-D-Xylosylzeatin	down	up	up	-0.58	1.58	1.17
Cholesterol	down	up	up	-0.78	7.22	2.68
4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-3-oxo-4-[(2E,6E)-farnesyl]-3,4-dihydroquinoline1-oxide	down	up	up	-0.43	0.91	2.60
Isoleucyl-Arginine	down	up	up	-0.22	1.23	2.01
Cocaine	down	up	up	-0.68	0.92	2.90
D-Maltose	down	up	up	-3.20	0.23	0.55
2-amino-2-deoxyglucitol-6-phosphate	down	up	up	-0.84	3.79	34.62
6-DeoxyerythronolideB	down	up	up	-0.72	2.18	2.57
Oripavine	down	up	up	-1.56	0.39	0.97
Dopaxanthinquinone	down	up	up	-0.33	0.36	0.72
Uridinemonophosphate (UMP)	down	up	up	-1.59	1.47	2.83
5-Hydroxyectoine	down	up	up	-0.11	0.58	1.41
Pentahomomethionine	down	up	up	-0.43	0.65	0.89
Tiglylcarnitine	down	up	up	-0.80	1.02	1.48
PS (18:1(11Z)/14:0)	down	up	up	-0.52	2.31	0.62
Guanidylicacid (guanosinemonophosphate)	down	up	up	-0.69	1.06	4.04
Nivalenol	down	up	up	-0.33	0.33	0.99

Atropine	down	up	up	-0.45	1.51	3.09
Lysyl-Isoleucine	down	up	up	-3.99	2.28	3.42
6alpha-Hydroxycampestanol	down	up	up	-1.85	2.85	2.04
Nonanoylcarnitine	down	up	up	-1.11	4.49	4.85
Glutamyl-Lysine	down	up	up	-0.33	0.73	1.84
Valyl-Lysine	down	up	up	-2.71	0.92	1.74
10-Deoxygeniposidicacid	down	up	up	-2.11	0.29	0.30
(S)-Piperidine-2-carboxamide	down	up	up	-1.04	0.51	0.92
(9Z)-Hexadecenoicacid	down	up	up	-0.86	4.54	2.06
4alpha-Carboxy-5alpha-cholesta-8,24-dien-3beta-ol	up	down	up	4.38	-3.17	30.84
ethyl-(2R)-methyl-(3S)-hydroxybutanoate	up	down	up	0.77	-0.60	2.89
PheGluProVal	up	down	up	0.56	-0.88	0.77
1-Methylpyrrolinium	up	down	up	0.17	-0.34	1.09
UDP-3-O-(3-hydroxytetradecanoyl)-N-acetylglucosamine	up	down	up	1.91	-1.57	3.44
m-Coumaricacid	up	down	up	0.55	-0.10	1.06
tryptophol	up	down	up	1.03	-0.61	1.27
gamma-L-Glutamylputrescine	up	down	up	0.93	-0.75	3.98
4-Vinylphenol	up	down	up	0.20	-0.21	0.89
4-Hydroxy-5-phenyltetrahydro-1,3-oxazin-2-one	up	down	up	2.04	-1.79	6.09
5-O-beta-D-Mycaminosyltylactone	up	down	up	3.50	-1.69	3.33
vitispirane	up	down	up	0.50	-0.63	0.77
gamma-amino-gamma-cyanobutanoicacid	up	down	up	2.15	-2.43	3.40
Asp-Phemethylester	up	down	up	0.45	-0.14	4.08
Calcidiol	up	down	up	3.44	-2.73	3.48
Sodiumlaurylsulfate	up	down	up	0.88	-0.34	0.33
PremithramycinA3	up	down	up	0.25	-0.79	0.24
β-estradiol	up	down	up	3.83	-1.45	3.00
2-Methyl-5-propylpyrazine	up	down	up	0.21	-0.38	0.20
L-d-1-Pyrroline-5-carboxylicacid	up	down	up	28.21	-1.13	28.21
N-Methylpelletierine	up	down	up	0.48	-0.48	2.14
4-Phosphopantothenoylcysteine	up	down	up	5.17	-0.88	10.94
1-ACETYLPYPERIDINE	up	down	up	1.41	-0.85	1.91
10-Deoxymethynolide	up	down	up	2.22	-1.63	2.23
3,3-Dimethylacrylicacid	up	down	up	1.07	-0.18	29.24

gabaculine	up	down	up	1.58	-0.47	4.24
L-Arogenate	up	down	up	0.45	-0.23	0.66
ubiquinone-0	up	down	up	3.74	-1.73	4.71
Deoxyguanidinoproclavaminicacid	up	down	up	0.22	-0.16	2.50
Cyclohexylisocyanide	up	down	up	28.67	-1.14	28.67
C20915	up	down	up	2.63	-0.49	2.61
Beta-Alanine	up	down	up	1.89	-0.47	4.88
Valyl-Isoleucine	up	down	up	28.23	-1.64	6.32
(N(omega)-L-arginino) succinicacid	up	down	up	4.26	-1.29	5.82
Tacrine	up	down	up	2.32	-1.85	1.80
1-Octen-3-ol	up	down	up	3.53	-1.72	6.56
cyclogutamate	up	down	up	5.16	-0.77	5.93
decoyinine	up	down	up	1.06	-3.07	8.24
L-Valine	up	down	up	1.05	-0.72	1.77
PI (16:1(9Z)/18:1(9Z))	up	down	up	0.34	-0.51	2.27
3-Hydroxy-N-glycyl-2,6-xylidine(3-Hydroxyglycinoxylidide)	up	down	up	0.44	-1.56	0.52
Norethindrone	up	down	up	3.61	-0.74	5.77
Androsta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione	up	down	up	3.62	-1.05	4.59
7,8-Dihydroneopterin	up	down	up	0.48	-0.34	2.39
4-Hydroxy-2,2'-bipyrrole-5-methanol	up	down	up	4.29	-5.89	6.23
Phytosphingosine 1-phosphate	up	down	up	1.20	-0.79	0.71
Picrocrocin	up	down	up	1.82	-1.05	1.68
Abscisate	up	down	up	0.19	-0.20	0.25
8-Amino-7-oxononanoicacid	up	down	up	3.34	-0.56	0.73
Pantothenicacid	up	down	up	3.17	-0.41	3.57
D-penicillamine	up	down	up	7.55	-1.36	29.02
Tetrahomomethionine	up	down	up	4.33	-0.84	31.02
Actinidine	up	down	up	6.84	-1.30	4.64
4-Allyl-2-methoxyphenol	up	down	up	3.39	-2.65	6.88
5-Hydroxyindoleacetate	up	down	up	1.04	-3.02	2.15
LEVULINICACID, 3-BENZYLIDENYL-	up	down	up	0.85	-0.81	0.82
3-mercaptohexan-1-ol	up	down	up	28.91	-0.72	28.91
4-Hydroxycinnamylaldehyde	up	down	up	0.72	-2.53	4.84
4-(3-Methylbut-2-enyl)-L-tryptophan	up	down	up	1.18	-1.03	4.52

Phenylalanyl-Histidine	up	down	up	1.15	-1.56	4.43
16alpha-Hydroxyestrone	up	down	up	2.84	-0.79	6.24
L-Phenylalanine	up	down	up	0.57	-0.55	2.72
Carmofur	up	down	up	2.04	-3.09	2.41
Norlinolenicacid	up	down	up	4.18	-0.65	3.97
Salidroside	up	down	up	3.31	-1.56	5.41
Tyramine	up	down	up	4.10	-0.93	6.38
gamma-Amino-gamma-cyanobutanoate	up	down	up	0.42	-1.53	1.68
(S)-Coclaurine	up	down	up	0.33	-0.26	1.84
Pseudooxynicotine	up	down	up	0.28	-0.36	0.96
N-Cyclopropylammelide	up	down	up	0.97	-0.75	0.96
Valyl-Proline	up	down	up	1.03	-0.33	30.94
4-Hydroxycinnamicacid	up	down	up	0.40	-0.25	1.24
zymosterolintermediate1c	up	down	up	1.99	-3.06	1.31
N-Acetyl-D-valine	up	down	up	1.30	-0.73	29.86
Toluene-cis-dihydrodiol	up	down	up	2.91	-2.93	27.29
Laccarin	up	down	up	0.16	-0.12	0.20
Abscisicalcohol	down	down	up	-1.33	-1.67	1.64
Dihydroergotamine	down	down	up	-0.06	-0.11	0.10
Glutathione	down	down	up	-0.39	-0.51	4.10
Nabumetone	down	down	up	-0.35	-0.98	0.37
Phenylalanyl-Isoleucine	down	down	up	-1.95	-0.72	4.67
Guanidinoproclavaminicacid	down	down	up	-0.25	-0.11	1.45
alpha-Isomethyl-ionone	down	down	up	-1.48	-1.19	1.91
1,6-anhMurNAc	down	down	up	-0.29	-0.35	0.23
RoquefortineD	down	down	down	-0.07	-0.11	-0.10
Trihomomethionine	down	down	down	-0.77	-0.57	-2.40

23

Note: VIP > 1 and $P < 0.05$.